

The P versus NP Problem

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P is the set of problems that can be solved efficiently in polynomial time.

NP is the set of problems whose solutions can be verified efficiently in polynomial time.

Representing the P vs. NP relationship through probabilities, where P is denoted by probability a and NP by probability b .

$$\mathbf{a + b = 1, 0 \leq a \leq 1, 0 \leq b \leq 1;}$$

$$\mathbf{k = \frac{b}{a}, 0 \leq k;}$$

$$\mathbf{a + ak = 1;}$$

$$\mathbf{a = \frac{1}{k + 1};}$$

$$\mathbf{b = \frac{k}{k + 1};}$$

$$\mathbf{\therefore P \neq NP, a + b = \frac{k+1}{k+1} = 1.}$$

Assuming the probability of P as a and NP as b , I substituted the ratio of their relationship as k .

The results show that $a = \frac{1}{k+1}$ and $b = \frac{k}{k+1}$, which demonstrates that P and NP are not equal, while their combined probability remains constant at 1.

However, when $k=1$, both sides become equal to $\frac{1}{2}$.